

Parenting Style and Its Relationship with Depression Among Adolescents

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ABSTRACT: Parenting style is one of the aspects that is often talked about by every parent and psychologists and it becomes a question of what parenting style is the best that needs to be practiced to ensure the well-being of children. Findings from studies by previous researchers have also found that parenting style is able to influence depression in adolescents. Therefore, this study was conducted for identify the relationship between parenting style and depression in circles teenagers. This study is a cross-sectional study using quantitative methods that is through use of questionnaires. The number of respondents involved in this study is a total of 158 teenagers who attended one of the schools in the Bandar Baru area Bangi, Selangor. Data were collected using simple sampling techniques and caim. The test tool used in this study was the Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ) which aims to look at the parenting style practiced by the respondents' parents and the Reynolds Adolescent Depression Scale (RADS) which aims to measure depression responden. The data obtained were analyzed descriptively and inferentially using SPSS 21. The results of the study found that authoritative parenting style has a negative relationship and significant with adolescent depression. This shows the parents who adopting an authoritative parenting style will reduce the rate of adolescent depression.

The results of a study on permissive and authoritarian parenting styles found that there were a positive and significant relationship between authoritarian and permissive parenting styles with adolescent depression. This indicates that the parents are adopting the style authoritarian and permissive parenting is capable of increasing adolescent depression. In conclusion, parents should adopt the best parenting style for ensuring the well-being of adolescents is guaranteed.

Keywords: Parenting style, adolescents, depression

I. INTRODUCTION

Parenting style is one of the important aspects in influencing the well-being of adolescent life. According to Russell et al., (2010), parenting style has strong correlations with adolescent self including in terms of academic achievement, manner adolescent problem solving, risky behaviors, mental health, self-esteem and depression. Parenting style is one of the important aspects in influencing the well-being of adolescent life. According to Russell et al., (2010), parenting style has strong correlations with adolescent self including in terms of academic achievement, manner adolescent problem solving, risky behaviors, mental health, self-esteem and depression. In general, parenting style can be defined as the method or manner of motherhood fathers in raising their children. There are various ways of parenting practiced by parents in raising children. Baumrind (1967) has divides parenting styles into three types namely authoritative, authoritarian and permissive. The differences of these three parenting styles are based on the level of intimacy and level parental control which refers to the term parental responsibility and parental demands on children (Omar et al., 2012).

Adopting parent the children. This is different with a parent adopting an authoritarian parenting style in which the parent adopts the style authoritarian parenting tends to have a high demand but have low accountability. Permissive parenting style is refers to parents who have a high degree of responsibility however has low demand. Depression, on the other hand, refers to a number of conditions in which an individual will feel sad, hopeless, grieving, lacking in enthusiasm and always feeling melancholy. According to Hettrington and Stanley (1997), depression that occurs in individuals will causing changes in cognitive and behavioral aspects. That change happening this is involving somatic symptoms i.e. those who suffer from it experience headache, irritability, tense and tired. What is more dangerous, the individual prone to prolonged depression is also at risk for suicide (Gotlibc & Ham men, 2009). Among the causes that can lead to the occurrence of deep depression adolescents are like genetics in which the adolescent inherits depression such from parents as well as social stress factors (Friedman & Anderson, 2011).

According to a study conducted by Suleiman et al., (2006), as much as 10.3 percent of the 2048 respondents surveyed suffered from depression. According to Suleiman et al.,(2006) again, among the causes of depression among adolescents that the teenager has many siblings, the distance between siblings is meetings and ineffective services by parents to children. In addition, the Study The 3rd National Health and Morbidity shows mental health problems was 11.2 percent among adults and 20.3 percent in the group of children --- children and adolescents as well as the leading cause of mental health problems is depression (Ministry of Health Malaysia, 2006). Although these statistics show a figure relatively small, however these findings also indicate the occurrence of depression in circles teenagers in Malaysia. In addition, findings from previous researchers also found depression experienced by adolescents will have a negative impact on adolescents such (Tsai et al., 2003; Sin & Lyubomirsky, 2009; Peluso et al., 2007).

The parenting style model articulated by previous researchers assumes that differences in parenting style practices practiced by parents will influence children's lives. For example, a study conducted by Driscoll et al., 2008; Cripps & Zyromski, 2009; Garcia & Gracia, 2009;) found that different parenting styles practiced by parents will affect the psychological well-being of children. This matter is in line with the opinion put forward by Goldenberg and Goldenberg (2008) in which way parenting style contributes a lot to children's behavior. By the way thus, parenting style turns out to be very important in building the generation of the time the best front. In the context of this study, the focus of the study is more focused on the effect of parenting style practiced by parents on deep depression among adolescents.

II. METHOD

2.1 Research Design

The study was conducted in the form of a survey using a questionnaire. Research methods this is a quantitative study. According to Rozmi Ismail (2013), the purpose of research quantitative done is aimed at testing theories, constructing facts and stating the relationship between the variables in the study in addition to knowing the cause and effect a phenomenon or problem occurs.

2.2 Study Sample

The study sample involved students in one of the schools in Bandar BaruBangi, Selangor who are between 13 and 15 years old. The selection of subjects in this study was done by using purposive sampling techniques. Subjects were selected based on age those categorized in the adolescent category. Number of subjects involved a total of 158 people.

Table 1: Distribution of study subjects by gender and age

		Bill (Percent %)
Gender	Boy	63 (39.9)
	Girl	95 (60.1)
	Amount	158 (100)
Age	14	21 (13.3)

	15	58 (36.7)
	16	79 (50.0)
Amount		158 (100)

2.3 Measurement Tool

To measure parenting style, the test tool used is Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ) developed by Buri (1991) to measure the concept of style parenting founded by Baumrind's (1971). This test tool is a questionnaire a self report containing 30 questions. PAQ also contains three types of styles parenting i.e. authoritarian, permissive and authoritative parenting styles. Every kind of style parenting contains ten items. Out of thirty items, twenty items are positive items while the other ten are negative items. Scales available in the Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ) is a likertshaped scale consisting of of the five answer choices. To measure depression, the test used is Reynolds The Adolescent Depression Scale (RADS) developed by Reynolds (1987). RADS contains 30 items divided into four scales. The scale is Dysphoric Mood, Anhedonia, Negative Self Evaluation and Somatic Complaints. Reynolds Adolescent The Depression Scale (RADS) is a test tool that measures depression with using a likertshaped scale consisting of four answer choices.

2.4 Data Analysis

The graded answers will be analyzed using the Statistical program Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 22. Data analysis in this study involved tests correlation. Correlation tests were used to look at the relationship between parenting styles with depression.

III. DECISION

Descriptive Analysis of Parenting Styles and Depression table 3.1 shows the mean and standard deviation values for the parenting style variables authoritarian, permissive parenting style, authoritative parenting style and depression. The mean value for the authoritarian parenting style variable was 27.22 with a standard deviation value of 6.84. Mean values for the permissive parenting style variable and authoritative are 20.92 and 37.47 with standard deviation values for both these variables are 6.84 and 5.81. Meanwhile, the mean value of the variable depression was 65.02 with a standard deviation value of 14.20.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation for the variables in the study

	Mean	S.p	Min	Max
Parenting Style				
Authoritarian	27.22	6.84	1.00	2.00
Permissive	20.92	6.84	10.00	45.00
Authoritative	37.47	5.81	18.00	50.00
Depression	65.02	14.20	32.00	106.00
Dysphoric Mood	17.81	4.12	8.00	29.00
Anhedonia	16.36	3.63	9.00	25.00
Negative self evaluating	16.58	4.19	8.00	30.00
Somatic Complaints	14.26	3.59	7.00	25.00

3.1 Decision Inference

Table 3.2 shows that there is a relationship between the three parenting styles with depression as a whole. As for authoritarian parenting styles, the findings of the study showed there was a significant positive relationship between parenting styles authoritarian with depression with r value obtained was $r = 0.252$, $k < 0.05$. At in addition, authoritarian parenting styles were also found to have a positive relationship and significant with dimensions of dysphoric mood, anhedonia, negative self evaluating and somatic complaints with a correlation value obtained was $r = 0.225$, $k < 0.05$ for dysphoric mood, $r = 0.315$, $k < 0.05$ for anhedonia, $r = 0.193$, $k < 0.05$ for negative self evaluating and $r = 0.194$, $k < 0.05$ for somatic complaints. This indicates the higher the style authoritarian parenting is practiced by parents, the higher the depression faced by children.

Table 3: Results of Correlation Test Between Parenting Style With Depression

	N	Depression	Dysphoric Mood	Anhedonia	Negative self evaluating	Somatic complaints
Parenting style						
Authoritarian	158	0.252**	0.225**	0.315**	0.193**	0.194**
Permissive	158	0.413**	0.402**	0.374**	0.365**	0.367**
Authoritative	158	-0.366**	-0.322**	-0.315**	-0.379**	-0.318**

$K < 0.05$

The findings of the study also show that permissive parenting styles have a relationship significant positive with depression with the value of r obtained is $r = 0.413$, $k < 0.05$. Permissive parenting styles were also found to have a positive relationship and significant with dimensions of dysphoric mood, anhedonia, negative self evaluating and somatic complaints with a correlation value obtained is $r = 0.402$, $k < 0.05$ for dysphoric mood, $r = 0.374$, $k < 0.05$ for anhedonia, $r = 0.365$, $k < 0.05$ for negative self evaluating and $r = 0.367$, $k < 0.05$ for somatic complaints. This indicates parents who adopt the style High permissive parenting will cause depression in children as well height. This is in contrast to the findings This is in contrast to the findings of studies on the relationship between styles authoritative parenting with depression. Findings of the study between the two enablers this variable indicates that there is a significant negative relationship between parenting styles authoritative with depression with r value obtained was $r = 0.366$, $k < 0.05$. All four dimensions of depression were also found to have a negative relationship and significant with parenting style where the value of r is obtained for the correlation between authoritative parenting style with dysphoric mood dimension was $r = 0.322$, $k < 0.05$, $r = 0.315$, $k < 0.05$ for anhedonia, $r = 0.379$, $k < 0.05$ for negative self evaluating and $r = 0.318$, $k < 0.05$ for somatic complaints. This indicates that the parents are adopting the style high authoritative parenting will cause the child's depression to be low.

IV. DISCUSSION

The findings of the study indicate that authoritarian and permissive parenting styles have a positive relationship with depression while an authoritative parenting style has a negative relationship with depression. This indicates the parents who adopt authoritarian and permissive parenting styles result in adolescence suffering from depression. While parents who adopt a parenting style authoritative also causes depression experienced by adolescents to be low. Findings previous studies have shown that authoritarian parenting styles have a relationship positive with depression while authoritative parenting style has a relationship negative with depression (Lipps et al., 2012; Sharma et al., 2011; O'Donnell et al., 2010). According to Gotlib and Hammen (2009), parents who have the characteristics of friendliness, be accepting, give autonomy consistently and always give reinforcement positive allows teens to see themselves and their world positively while parenting who are critical, rejecting and controlling cause teenagers to look at themselves and their world in a negative way. In the context of parents who adopt a parenting style authoritative, parents who practice this style of

parenting tend to be friendly and giving teens the opportunity to express opinions causes teens to be a positive and respected person. This is in line with that opinion presented by Decay and Kenny (1997) where adolescents are psychologically frequent want other individuals to listen and give them a chance to give views, express feelings and gain respect from other individuals. Taste that this positive can indirectly prevent adolescents from experiencing depression.

However, this is the opposite of parenting style authoritarian where the authoritarian parenting style is too strict, punitive and not listening to the views of teenagers will make teenagers feel constrained and inadvertently will directly disrupt the psychological well-being of adolescents. Parental attitudes this overly constricting causes adolescent psychosocial needs such as desires for freedom, the desire for autonomy, as well as the desire to form a limited self-identity (Ismail et al., 2008). According to Goodyer (2001), among the social factors that contribute to adolescent depression is a parental attitude that is too assertive and does not give space to them for self-defense. If viewed through Maslow's hierarchy of needs (1970), among the needs for an individual is the need for respect from other people. Parental attitudes that are too strict and punitive cause teenagers feel themselves disrespected by their parents and this indirectly can contribute to increased depression. In addition, according to Ismail et al., (2008), psychosocial characteristics of children raised in adoptive families authoritarian parenting style is moderate academic achievement, social skills who are weak and often suffer from depression.

The findings also show that there is a positive and significant relationship between permissive parenting style with depression. The findings of this study are in line with the findings of a study conducted by Milevsky et al., (2007) in which the findings of his study found that parents who adopted a permissive parenting style were found to contribute in increasing depression compared to authoritative parenting styles. Parents that too much allows and obeys the will of the teenager will result in the teenager not get good guidance and advice in living their lives. According to Ismail et al., (2008), even adolescents always want the freedom to perform what is liked, yet teenagers at the same time still need help and parental guidance. The attitude of parents who are too obedient and always give praise to children causes adolescents' concept and self-efficacy to be too high and unrealistic (Ismail et al., 2008). This causes if teenagers experience something failure in their lives, tolerance for such failure is low and indirectly cause depression.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, parenting style is a very important aspect in affecting the psychological well being of adolescents. Parents who adopt style authoritarian and permissive parenting will be able to increase adolescent depression while authoritative parenting styles can reduce adolescent depression. By In that case, parents should choose the best parenting style for ensuring teenagers can live life well.

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